

FEMALE BROODSTOCK SIZE AND RESPONSE TO SELECTION FOR THE WEIGHT OF *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell)

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ABSTRACT

The correlation between the weight of catfish female broodstock and the growth rate of their offspring has been a significant focus for fish producers. This study looked at the induced breeding of African catfish, *Clarias gariepinus*, to examine its response to selection for the weight of the female broodstock. The experiment was set up in a completely-randomized-design (CRD) with treatment combinations as; average weight of the female size categories 1000g (Treatment I or Small size), 1500g (Treatment II or Medium size) and 2500g (Treatment III or Large size). There was no significant fluctuation in the physicochemical parameters of the water. The result showed that direct responses to one generation of selection for the three Treatments were in ascending order, 11.99%, 16.26% and 23.02% for Treatments 1, Treatments 111 and Treatments 11 respectively. Overall, the results of these growth evaluations showed that the selected group had improved growth performance and the selection response achieved in the trials was apparent in all Treatments. Medium-sized female broodstock can therefore deliver substantial genetic improvements in the induced breeding of *C. gariepinus*

Keywords; progeny, selection response, F1 generation, *Clarias gariepinus*

INTRODUCTION

There is an increase in global fish production which can be attributed to the heightened involvement in aquaculture and its current innovative advances. This demand for aquaculture has emerged in response to the declining output from capture fisheries causes of which Kearney & Hilborn, (2022) identified as overfishing, and illegal fishing amongst others. Whereas capture fisheries have experienced a decline from 92.2 billion metric tonnes in 2019 this declined to 90.3 billion metric tonnes in 2020, aquaculture's contribution to global fish production has

increased from 85.2 billion metric tonnes in 2019 to 87.5 billion metric tonnes thus leveraging increase in global fish production from 2019-2020 (FAO, 2022). The increasing significance of aquaculture has driven advancements in the technologies (Rowan, 2023) essential for fulfilling the critical needs of efficient fish farming *vis a vis*: the generation of fish seeds for stocking alongside the supply of high-quality nutrition and the upkeep of optimal water conditions. (Kaur *et al.*, 2023).

In Nigeria, the production distribution of major cultured species is as follows: Tilapia 5.4%, Carp 14.6%, Catfish 73.2%, Ornamental 5.4%, and Others 1.8% (Ozigbo *et al.*, 2014). Particularly noteworthy is the resilience of the African catfish species, *Clarias gariepinus*, identified by Olagunju *et al.* (2023), as highly accepted and valued in Nigerian aquaculture (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2020). Historically, catfish did not reproduce in captivity. However, recent research indicates that photoperiod manipulation has induced natural spawning in butter catfish *Ompok bimaculatus* during non-spawning seasons (Ajithkumar *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, out-of-season spawning of channel catfish *Ictalurus punctatus* has been achieved through photothermal and hormonal manipulations (ICLARM; now the WorldFish Center) and the Institute for Aquaculture Research in Norway along with aquaculture systems (Kutler & Koc, 1996) proposed ways (Murray, 2005) and development effort to genetically improve farmed tilapia, aiming to enhance productivity, while maintaining environmental safeguards and sustainability (Murray, 2005) fish seeds remains low. Consequently, there is a growing emphasis on artificial fish propagation to ensure a consistent supply of high-quality seeds, crucial for enhancing aquaculture production. Artificial propagation, as highlighted by Egwenomhe *et al.* (2020), is considered the most promising and reliable method for ensuring the year-round availability of superior fish seeds and the sustainability of the aquaculture industry. Achieving the production of such quality seeds relies on adopting proper breeding practices and leveraging biotechnology (Achegbulu *et al.*, 2013).

The central focus of breeding programs emphasizes the broodstock, which plays a pivotal role in influencing the quality of

offspring and, consequently, the overall production of fish. Selection is the primary breeding programme targeted at the broodstock, and directs to a large degree the quality of offspring, and subsequently fish production. The staggering growth of aquaculture has long been shown to be due to a lack of adequate attention to genetics and selective breeding, leading to stagnating yields unlike the longstanding practice of selective breeding in terrestrial animal farming, the genetic aspects of fish farming (Afewerki *et al.*, 2023), including tilapia farming, were disregarded until the mid-1980s. (Geletu, & Zhao, 2023). The repercussions of this oversight became apparent in the form of stagnating tilapia yields. In response, the International Center for Living Aquatic Resources Management

The decline in yield can result from the combined effects of selection in the wrong direction and inbreeding, leading to significant variations in fish size, low survival rates, slow growth, and inefficient feed conversion ratios. These factors ultimately contribute to poor returns on farming. Ponzoni *et al.* (2012) have made efforts to elucidate the genetic basis of stock performance deterioration and recommend methods to prevent it. Genetic technologies can be harnessed in aquaculture for various purposes, including improvements in production, marketing, and the conservation of natural resources (Bartley, 1998). While biotechnology has

development of genetic resources in aquaculture, its application in Africa has faced constraints due to safety concerns associated with certain breeding programs (Changadeya *et al.*, 2003). Consequently, there is a reliance on selective breeding and hybridization to enhance genetic resources in aquaculture.

This work aims to initiate a genetic breeding program, specifically employing the traditional selective breeding approach, to provide data for the directional filtering of traits in the African Catfish *Clarias gariepinus*. The focus is on evaluating the selection response for the weight of female

C. gariepinus

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted within a period of 18 months at the fish hatchery facility of Marine Farms. Marine Farms has a reputable hatchery, and it is located at No.2 Orogun Street, Isiohor Village, Benin City.

Preparation of fish hatchery and culture tanks

One concrete grow-out tank (10m x 12.5m x 1.5m), three rectangular hatchery tanks (2.3m x 1.0m x 1.0m) each partitioned into 3 compartments, nine 5 l plastic bowls, nine 60 l plastic aquaria, and nine grow-out ponds (2m x 8m x 1.5m), were used for this study. The tanks were washed using a detergent and a disinfectant and properly rinsed with clean water prior to impoundment with water. Grow-out tanks were fertilized to raise plankton prior to stocking, while in the hatchery tanks, the kakabans were laid overnight inside clean water of about 0.3m depth. Broodstock tank and grow-out tanks were filled with borehole water to 0.8m depth from a nearby borehole via an overhead tank all within the farm. The nursery ponds were filled with water up to about 0.6-1m depth.

Selection of experimental fish

I. Selection of foundation stock (500 fingerlings)

500 fingerlings of *Clarias gariepinus* were selected from a reputable hatchery in Benin City based on uniformity of size, age, health status (only fish seeds that are healthy and active), nutritional history (all fish seeds raised on the same diet) and parental origin (all fish seed raised from the same parents). These fingerlings were raised for 12 months.

I. Selection of broodstock from the foundation stock (selection within cohort)

From the foundation population (500 individuals), using an individual selection method based on biological fitness and

weight, one-year-old *Clarias gariepinus* females with average weight categories of 1kg, 1.5kg and 2.5kg were selected (Plate 1). The biological fitness was based on the presence of a round and turgid papilla, the softness of the abdomen and the uniform size of intra-ovarian oocytes as selection criteria (Sahoo *et al.*, 2004). Oocytes were obtained by applying a slight pressure on the abdomen. Thirty to forty oocytes were selected randomly and measured using a micrometre screw gauge. The selected females were grouped into three categories based on their weights e.g. 1,000g, 1,500g and 2,500g. Each of these weight categories represented a Treatment. II. Selection of male broodstock (3 males)

Individual selection method was used to also obtain the males, progeny of a different set of parents, weighing about 2.5-3kg each, were sourced from a farm in Ibadan, South-West Nigeria and selected on the basis of elongated and turgid, reddish genital papilla (Egwenomhe and Obi 2012). One male was used for each of the 3 trials. Eggs obtained from a total of 9 selected females and milt from one selected male were used for the breeding performance study for each trial.

Experimental design A total of 500 fingerlings, which selection response was measured, were used as starter experimental material (fish) from which the three treatments were selected based on the average size of the female broodstock. The three-trial experiment was setup in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) where the broodstocks were allotted

Plate 1: Nine broodstock of 3 different size categories

Plate 2: Nops table weighing scale 5000g capacity, Graduation 40g with a background showing the experimental layout

Experimental procedure Selective breeding technology, specifically, traditional selective breeding, (i.e. individuals were selected based on weight, a phenotypic trait) was used in measuring the maternal effect on size as a response to selection. Rearing of the selected five hundred (500) post fingerlings for 12 months thus providing broodstock recruitment and data for population variance; The fish were stocked in a concrete grow-out pond (10m x 12.5m x 1.5m) at four fish per meter square (Ozigbo *et al.*, 2014). The fish were fed to satiation with a 40% crude protein commercial feed. Feeding was done twice daily in the morning (10.00hrs) and evening (16.00hrs). Pond water quality was maintained by regular flushing while raising the fish for 12 months to ensure sexual maturity.

At maturity, from the 500 foundation stock, the 3-size category was selected and spawned. Larvae were fed to satiation twice daily with dried decapsulated cysts of *Artemia salina* nauplii. After one week of feeding, the fish were introduced gradually to the artificial dry diet of 200 – 300 µm catfish feed. Artemia and the artificial dry diet were offered alternately to the larvae during the weaning period which lasted for four days.

Rearing of 14 days fry for another 35 days was done using nine 60l plastic tanks out the door. Fish larvae were fed 0.5mm commercial feed till fish were 25 days old and subsequently fed *ad lib* with 43% crude protein 0.8-1.2mm feed till fish were 49 days old.

Rearing 10 weeks (fingerlings) old fish seed to table size (6 months) was done using nine concrete grow-out ponds (i.e. 2m x 8m x 1.5m). The fingerlings were stocked in the grow-out ponds at 200 fish per weight category (i.e. 12 fish per m²). The sizes of the fingerlings were carefully selected for even a match to avoid death via cannibalism. Also,

each tank had fingerlings from each size category to nullify possible environmental influence in the result. The fish were fed to satiation with a 40% crude protein commercial feed throughout the culture period. The fish were fed in the morning (10.00hrs) and evening (16.00hrs). Water quality was maintained through occasional flushing and fish were cultured for 6 months to table size.

Measurement of water quality parameters

This was done at 6 days interval throughout the culture period to ensure optimum water quality throughout the culture. DO was measured *in situ* with WTM, Oxical-SL

portable electronic probe, pH and ®

Temperature were monitored using AZ pH meter Pen type (Model; 8685) and adequate oxygen level (above 5mg/l) was maintained with RESUN LP- 100 low noise air-pump. Ammonia and Nitrate were measured with the aid of a visible spectrophotometer after they had been treated with Nessler's reagent. Total Alkalinity was measured by titration method.

Data collection

Data were collected as follows: Broodstock recruitment and data for population variance from the rearing of five hundred (500) post fingerlings for 12 months.

The population's mean weight, minimum and maximum weights, as well as the mean weight of male and female of the 500 fish, were taken when the fish were 8 months old i.e. at the age of recruitment into broodstock. The broodstock was conditioned for another 2 months to guarantee the full maturity of the fish. The data on population growth parameters were used to compute response to selection.

The selection response of *C. gariepinus* for selected broodstock weight (R) was computed as;

$- = -h^2$ (Falcona, 1989)

R= Response (gain/loss) per generation

S= Selection differential or reach (i.e. the superiority or inferiority of generation over the initial population average)

$S = \frac{\text{mean wt of selected females} + \text{mean wt of selected males} - \text{Pop. Mean wt.}}{2}$

$h^2 = \text{proportionate amount of } V_A$ ($V_A = \text{Additional variance} = 0.5$ (a constant))

The response of the first filial generation F_1 , also known as the first response was calculated as;

$F_1 = \text{Population mean} + R$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Water Quality Parameters There was no significant fluctuation in the physicochemical parameters of the water. The values of the parameters were within optimal range. Dissolve oxygen, ammonia, and total alkalinity concentrations varied from 5.8, 0.18, and 120 (minimum) to 6.7, 0.28, and 128 (maximum) mg/l, respectively. The mean water quality parameters values

observed (Temperature, DO, pH) were within the recommended range for fish culture (Boyd & Tucker, 1998). This suggests that the parameters did not seem to negatively influence the test fish in this study. The optimal water condition was maintained for the fish throughout the experiment to forestall undue influence on fish growth. Response to Selection

Table 1: First response to selection (estimated) RF_1 , mean weight (g) of F_1 at recruitment WF_1 , and direct response to one generation of selection (R_{DF1}) of the F_1 .

Treatments	RF_1 (g)	WF_1 (g)	R_{DF1} %
1 (small size)	562.50	626.27	11.99
11 (medium size)	562.50	686.33	23.02
111 (big size)	562.50	653.33	16.20

Source: field study

Direct responses to one generation of selection for the three Treatments were in ascending order 11.99%, 16.26% and 23.02% for Treatment 1. Treatments 111 and Treatments 11 respectively.

$R = \text{Response (gain/loss) per generation} = 12.5\text{g}$

$F = \text{The response of the first filial generation, also known as the first response was estimated according to Falcona (1989)} = 562.5\text{g.}$

$F = 562.5\text{g.}$

Treatment 1 = 1,006.67g,

Treatment 11 = 1,231.67g,

Treatment 111 = 1,156.67g

There was no f_2 response concern as the population was split into 3 treatments and could no longer be regarded as a population.

Akinwande, *et al.*, (2017) reported a direct response to one generation of selection for the H(high) and L(low) growth to be 5.44% and 4.78% respectively with an average of 5.11% in both groups in a study of the selection response and heritability estimate for growth in the Giant African Catfish (*Heterobranchus dorsalis*) Geoffroy Saint – Hilaire, 1809). About 12-18% response to selection for growth were obtained in three strains of the channel catfish (*Ictalurus punctatus*) after one generation of selection (Dunham and Smitherman, 1983), 14.4% in *Salmon salar* (Gjerde 1986), 7-9% in the Nile tilapia and 7% in *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (Kause *et al.*, 2005). In shellfishes (Nell *et al.*, 1996) obtained a 4% increase in growth rate in the Sydney-rock oyster (*Saccostrea commercialis*), while the Chilean oyster (*Ostrea chilesis*) showed a 10-13% gain after one generation of

selection (Toro *et al.*, 1995). In shrimps, selection response in the Kurama prawn (*Marsupenaeus japonicus*) was 10.7% (Hetzel *et al.*, 2000), while in the Pacific White shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) a 21% increase in growth was observed after one generation of selection (Argue *et al.*, 2012). The average mean weight of *H. bidorsalis* obtained from the base population from which 9 selections were made in this study, was lower than the average weight (850g) obtained in *H. dorsalis* raised in a semi-intensive pond culture system as reported (Owodeinde 2012) at 7 months of culture. This could be due to the lower stocking density ($> 1\text{fish/m}^2$) applied, initial fertilization of the pond which boosted primary productivity, and higher dietary crude protein level (45%) of feed used in that study.

CONCLUSION

The selected group consistently had higher final body weights in the three Treatments. Overall, the results of these growth evaluations showed that the selected group of female offspring had improved growth performance and the selection response achieved in the trials was apparent in all Treatments. Medium sized female broodstock can therefore deliver substantial genetic improvements in induced breeding of *C. gariepinus*. This is because efficient and sustainable genetic improvement work involves: balanced selection for traits that primarily reduce production cost (growth rate, feed conversion efficiency, survival); among other traits.

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